

**Impact of Horror Movies on Anxiety Among Senior High School Students in Cebu
Institute of Technology University**

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Abstract

This study will determine the effect of watching horror movies on anxiety levels. The researchers hypothesized that the horror genre would make people more anxious after watching such a film. Sixteen (16) senior high school students from the Cebu Institute of Technology-University aged 16-18 years old were the participants of the research. State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) was used in the experiment to measure the state-anxiety level of the participants before and after watching the short horror film. The researchers utilized a one-group pretest-posttest design or a quasi-experimental approach. Initially, the participants took a pretest using the STAI to establish the baseline score. The subjects then watched a 16-minute-short horror movie, entitled "The Last Séance". After which, the participants retook the STAI as posttest to examine whether a change of scores occurred. The computed mean of anxiety scores before watching the movie is lower than the mean after watching the movie ($45.88 < 47.13$). The t-test analysis revealed that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected ($t \text{ stat } -0.59 < CV \ 2.13$; $p\text{-value } 0.56 > \alpha$). Hence, the findings suggest that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the two samples and an increase in state-anxiety level among the participants after watching a horror movie is nonexistent. These results, however, cannot be generalized. A similar study should be conducted with a greater sample to see differences or similarities with the current study.

Keywords: anxiety, fear, horror movies

Impact of horror movies on anxiety

In today's time, movies are one of the biggest sources of entertainment. Most people love to watch movies and one of the most popular and profitable film genres is horror movies. Horror movies are designed to evoke negative emotions in viewers such as fears, dread, and disgust, also it can trigger unwanted thoughts and feelings and increase levels of anxiety (Bartsch et al., 2010)

Although horror movies are scary, gross, and make people think about death and fear for their lives, many people still think that horror movies are a blast to watch (Patti Greco, 2020). Some people would say that, even though horror movies would make them feel scared and anxious, these feelings or reactions are also the reason they feel fun and excitement while watching the film. However, regardless of these feelings of fun and excitement, viewing a frightening film can create severe cases of anxiety, horror of dying, dizziness, increased heartbeat, and feeling of shortness of breath (Aluja-Fabregat & Torrubia-Beltri, 1998).

According to Glenn Sparks, horror films provide people with a physiological arousal, which includes an increase in heart rate, systolic blood pressure, and respiration rate that might trigger a person's feelings of being vigorous, energized, and anxious. Anxiety can also be an effect of watching scary movies. Watching horror genre films can be a factor that might cause a person to have anxiety, and or, this can also be a factor that could trigger someone's anxiety. Scary movies could produce a serious cause of anxiety in teens and even pre-teens (Maria Lopez, 2015).

Young people know that horror films or the characters in those films do not exist, but it is observed that young people are afraid of these films. To Morreall (1993), fear can take many more inanimate forms – we do not have to physically see a tornado to be afraid of one. In addition, we can be afraid of others, which is the

common case for moviegoers. They do not usually fear for their own life, unless they suffer from some form of psychosis, but they fear for the life of the character on the screen. However, many studies have shown how horror movies can trigger anxiety development in adolescents. The researchers chose this topic to understand how these horror movies affect the mental health of teenagers and induce aggressive and disturbing behaviors due to such movies.

This study aims to investigate the impact of horror movies on anxiety among adolescents. An experiment is conducted through a virtual experiment with a group of 16–18-year-old individuals. The findings of this study will bring understanding of how emotions are generated and processed and may help us understand elements of anxiety and fear of watching horror movies.

Genre Theory

Grossberg (1998) outlined three theories of meaning in terms of discussing the relationships of genres. He claimed that there are three most used terms in defining genre using the theories of meaning. The first approach is “genre’s set of conventions” (Grossberg, p.160). These conventions are camera technique, sounds, and lighting. In this approach, the use of these conventions will create an impact on the viewers which makes the horror film better. As some horror movies have low lighting, terrible use of sound, and terrible camera angle which makes the movie horrible. This set of conventions are crucial in a horror film as it creates fear in the viewers. The second approach which Grossberg defines is “the underlying structure of values that the genre puts into play” (Grossberg, p.161). This sets the viewer's expectations of the film. Many horror watchers anticipate seeing a struggle between the 'unknown', with an unforeseen casualty within the horror genre. These expectations shape the experience of the viewers in watching horror movies. According to Kristina Gold (2003-2004), horror movies can effectively trick us into

accepting that something may be conceivable within the real world. Horror movies, when executed well, by setting less dependence on horrifying uncommon impacts, it can be an extremely powerful film form. It permits the film to tap into audiences dream states, the horror of the nonsensical, the unknown and the horror within man himself. ("SOSC4319 Home"). "Genres can be seen as articulations of texts that define a particular set of intertextual relations" (Grossberg, p.161). Grossberg's third approach and third theory of meaning. According to him, genres tell us how to peruse a specific content by setting it into more familiar structures of meaning. Horror films are often recognized for their emotional effect on the viewer. It aims to scare, shock, terrify, and repel. In addition, Grossberg claimed that genres are not stable and simple categories, and that it constantly changing. Given what has been said, there is a structure of meaning as to how the watcher or audiences decipher the films.

Experience

Many studies showed how horror movies initiate an impact of the development of anxiety among adolescents. According to a recent study conducted by Khan et al. (2020), watching horror movies could often create confusion to the viewers about what is "real" and what is "not" in their experiences. For example, watching horror movies could trigger thinking that there is something going on behind you, such as hallucinations, overthinking, and deep fear. Horror movies may be used to recall horrible experiences and could also influence psychological and neurobiological responses.

According to the study of Park (2018), although watching horror movies can make people anxious and scared, people still enjoy watching the thrill one after another. She claimed that people watch horror films because it helps release anxiety and fears deep inside the consciousness of the people. Moreover, she highlights Sigmund Freud's theory of psychoanalysis, a belief that all individuals have

unconscious thoughts, feelings, wants, and recollections. According to Freud's theory horror films come from the uncanny, a dread we feel from the emergence of images and thoughts from the primitive id. Horror movies highlight desires, and the thoughts that are buried deep inside our subconscious. She also claimed based on the theory of the Greek philosopher Aristotle, which is catharsis, that by watching scary movies it releases negative emotions and worries about the real world. Aside from that, people enjoy watching horror movies because they can take part in the characters' adventure, and that it arouses the consciousness that keeps it alert. Park (2018) gave eight theories on why people watch horror films. One of those theories said that "fear is a negative emotion that comes about when people are under siege or threat," Professor Glen Sparks told Seeker, media of discovery. People watch horror films because they enjoy fear, they enjoy the experience that comes with fear. According to Seeker, "for certain individuals, the desire to feel fear is a manifestation of an adrenaline-seeking personality." ("The Aesthetics and Psychology Behind Horror Films").

Anxiety

Nummenmaa (2021) expressed that the mental and neurobiological reactions are created from what our brain conceives as a programmed fear reaction or reality while watching horror movies. Secondary experiences, phobias, termination, and life-threatening experiences are some examples of universal themes in horror movies. Secondary experiences are the most efficient mechanism that allows the viewers to interact with the movie. When an individual is anxious, a response will automatically start that could lead to a sign of anxiety and, sometimes, could lead to a negative response such as aggression.

Straube et al. (2009) conducted a study which aims to investigate the neural relationships of being frightened when seeing terrifying movies, and the affiliation

between the personality trait sensation seeking and brain activation amid frightening movie clips. The study yielded three fundamental results related to the impacts of movie category, experienced anxiety, and personality. The study showed that threat, as compared to neutral scenes of scary movie clips, lead to increased activation in the ACC, anterior insula, thalamus, and visual areas related emphatically with actuation in dorsomedial prefrontal cortex, showing a part for this range within the subjective involvement of being frightened.

In this study, the researchers intend to postulate that if a person watches a horror movie which gives a good scare, then the impact of horror on anxiety will increase. Furthermore, this study adheres to the idea of how horror movies could affect anxiety. This study focuses on examining the impact of horror movies on anxiety on senior high school students in Cebu Institute of Technology - University.

Method

Participants

Sixteen (16) senior high school students from Cebu Institute of Technology-University, male and female with ages ranging from 16 to 18 years old voluntarily took part in the conducted virtual experiment.

Measure

The STAI (State-Trait Anxiety Inventory) is a widely used test of trait and state anxiety. According to (Spielberger, Gorsuch, Lushene, Vagg, & Jacobs, 1983), this is a reliable predictor of caregiver distress over time, and it fluctuates when support systems, wellness, and other personal characteristics change. It can also help objectively analyze and rate the level of anxiety experienced by the participants. The overall score varies from 0 to 63. Scores should be interpreted using the following guidelines: 0–9, no anxiety; 10–18, mild to moderate anxiety; 19–29, moderate to

severe anxiety; and 30–63, severe anxiety. This measurement instrument Shape Y has 20 items for surveying state anxiety, this incorporates: “I am tense; I am worried” and “I feel calm; I feel secure”. Internal consistency coefficients for the scale have extended from .86 to .95; test-retest reliability coefficients have extended from .65 to .75 over a 2-month interval (Spielberger et al., 1983). Test-retest coefficients for this measure in the present study ranged from .69 to .89. Noteworthy evidence attests to the construct and concurrent validity of the scale (Spielberger, 1989). The STAI scale does not have any subscale test.

A short horror film about 16 minutes long is entitled, “The Last Séance” (2018), presented by ALTER and is directed by Laura Kulik. This film has received one million views. This is the second research measure to examine or assess the level of anxiety and functioning of the participants. Researchers have validated this movie to horror enthusiasts and given it a high rating. Furthermore, this film garnered favorable ratings from the two main review sites. In IMDB, there are 53 users that are 25 males and 7 females aged 18 to 45 and above who rated this film. It was rated 6.5 out of 10 given by its users. In the second review site, Letterboxd, based on 123 ratings the average weight is 3.05. According to the limits of the study, the evaluations, and users on these two review sites, seeing this film with parental guidance is advised.

Procedures

One week before the experiment, informed consent forms were sent out to the target participants explaining the details of the experiment and were returned to the researchers signed and agreed. In this study, a quasi-experimental approach was used (one-group pretest posttest design). On the set day of the experiment, the researchers and the participants met in a virtual platform which also served as the experimental room. The experiment began by letting the 16 participants answer the

State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) through a google form. Afterwards, the participants watched the 16-minute horror movie, "The Last Séance", without intervention. Right after the movie finished, the participants answered another google form of the same STAI questionnaire. After the experiment, the participants were debriefed about the activity and were given token of appreciation for their voluntary participation.

Data Analysis

After the data was obtained, the researchers employed a t-test for dependent samples. It is the right statistical analysis to be used since the study follows one group pretest posttest design. The same subjects (16 participants) are being observed in the two samples: (1) anxiety level before watching the horror movie and (2) anxiety level after watching the horror movie. These two samples are dependent and using paired t-test, the researchers will know if the mean change for these pairs is significantly different from zero. The analysis then determined whether the researcher rejects or does not reject the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis.

Ethical Consideration

The study requires virtual engagement and personal information from the participants therefore in need of reliance and confidence. Hence, the researchers guaranteed the participants safety and confidentiality. Before the experiment started, screening was done as well as parents' consent was asked to ensure no harm will be experienced by the participants. The experiment is completely voluntary. Any participants who wish to exit shall not be kept on hold. Personal information from the participants will be kept private. Confidentiality of any personal information is assured as well as anonymity for the participants. Only relevant data components were collected and presented.

Results and Discussions

This study is conducted with a hypothesis that there will be a difference in the anxiety levels of the research participants before and after watching a short horror movie. Specifically, the participants are expected to have an increased anxiety after watching the movie. The corresponding results of the study are presented as follows:

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Mean scores of participants' anxiety before and after watching a horror movie

	<i>Before watching a horror movie</i>	<i>After watching a horror movie</i>
Mean	45.88	47.13
Standard Deviation	4.29	6.11
Observations	16	16
df	15	

The table shows that the mean of the first sample is 45.88 indicative of severe anxiety with a standard deviation of 4.29. The second sample has a mean of 47.13 with a standard deviation of 6.11 indicative of severe anxiety as well. This suggests that the participants have severe anxiety before and after watching the horror movie. The difference observed in the mean scores ($45.88 < 47.13 = 1.25$) is suggestive of an

increase in state anxiety level however too small to conclude its significance for a 16-responder study with 15 degrees of freedom until a statistical analysis is performed.

This may follow the suggestion of Miller-Shreve (2018), that individual's reactions to anxiety-inducing stimuli, such as horror movies, have been proven to be influenced by personal qualities. Horror films are intended to frighten you, disgust, shock, and extreme instability. "A good horror story is one that functions on a symbolic level, using fictional (and sometimes supernatural) events to help us understand our own deepest real fears." (King, 2010). What causes fear? Fear and its etiology have a long history in psychology, and various models have been proposed to explain why we become afraid and to what types of stimuli we are afraid (Öhman and Mineka, 2001).

However, it depends on the type of horror you are watching: One view of horror considers it to be of two types: horror, which is genuine and is designed to make us afraid because it is advantageous to our survival (e.g., fear arising from attack and being motivated to fight or flee), and art horror, which describes the imagined horror found in horror films (Carroll, 1987). Anyhow, some people who suffer from anxiety may find horror films soothing. While horror films are not a true alternative to seeking help if you need it. For people who experience anxiety this would create a flight or fight response towards those things. They know, it is not real or at least, some parts of our brain know it is not real. Other parts of ancient structures located in the limbic system respond as though it were real. (Moss, 2017).

T-test Analysis

Table 2

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

t Stat	-0.59
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P(T<=t) two-tail	0.56
t Critical two-tail	2.13

**Note: level of significance $p= 0.05$*

Using a dependent t-test, the data reveals that the mean difference observed in the two samples is not statistically significant with a determined statistic value very much smaller than the critical value (t stat $-0.59 < CV 2.13$) and a p-value greater than the set level of significance (p-value $0.56 > \alpha 0.05$). The findings show that the researchers have failed to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant increase in the state-anxiety level of the participants after watching the horror movie.

Some people watch horror movies to be scared and anxious because it feels fun and exciting. Aluja-Fabregat and Torrubia-Beltri (1998) claimed that regardless of these fun and excitement, frightening films can still create severe cases of anxiety along with other heightened physiological reactions. The results of the current study contradict this claim by revealing a small difference between the pre- and post-treatment mean scores.

As we cannot deny the fact that horror films have a way of attracting a large audience. Horror movies can make an impact on one's emotions, they can trigger anxiety, or they can help with anxiety. According to Michelle Park (2018), her study claims that individuals enjoy viewing horror films because they help them release worry and worries that are deep inside their awareness. In relation to a study by Madan et al (2013), they have examined that the youth worry is linked to media violence, although the cause of the impact has not been determined, however, they have claimed that individuals who saw violent movie snippets had more anxiety rather than those who watched the non-violent movie.

In contradiction, the research findings of Straube, T. et al. (2009) led that neutral movie scenes of horror movies clips lead to increased activation in the ACC, anterior insula, thalamus, and visual areas related emphatically with activation in the dorsomedial prefrontal cortex, showing a part for this range within the subjective involvement of being frightened. Models that predict brain hypoactivation in high sensation seekers amid neutral stimulus corroborated their findings, which might be compensated by more intense sensations such as watching horrifying movie clips.

Furthermore, as in other research by Scrivner and Christensen (2021), although horror is intended to provoke dread and anxiety in its audience, many people with anxiety are horror lovers, and others describe adopting horror to cope with their anxiety. They offer a theoretical explanation for why people suffering from anxiety may seek solace in horror films.

Conclusion

This research studies the impact of watching horror movies on the level of anxiety of Senior High School Students in Grade 11-Versatility from Cebu Institute of Technology University. The primary data was collected by giving out a form to the 16 selected participants who will be taking part in the virtual experiment. As mentioned earlier in the introduction, the purpose of this study was to adhere to the idea of how horror movies could affect anxiety while if a person watches a horror movie which gives a good scare, then the impact of horror movie on anxiety increases.

Based on the analysis as mentioned above, it can be concluded that there is no significant impact on the anxiety level of a person when watching a horror movie film. This just means that horror films do not affect nor trigger the anxiety of a person. However, these findings still cannot be generalized to other people. The same study needs to be conducted with other people or students from other universities to see if there are any differences or similarities that could support and help on adding more information and knowledge for the future researchers of the same study.

Limitations of Existing Research

The study is conducted online therefore, researchers and participants are not together in one physical room and have different environments. The difference in lighting, ventilation, and noise may affect the concentration of the participants while watching the movie as well as their state of being. The movie experience may also not be all-out because the movie is played only through smartphones and/or laptops, not on large screens. The stability of each participant's internet may also affect the smoothness of the movie on their ends and so their experience of watching the movie. Furthermore, the number of participants is insufficient to detect a meaningful change in scores before and after the participants saw the horror film.

Directions for Future Research

Future researchers are recommended to run an experiment with a diverse range of participant levels. If attainable, choose a movie with a lengthier duration rather than a 16-minute film when researchers may have a 1-hour movie or so. This would accurately reflect its influence on the target participants' degree of anxiety. This way, researchers could evaluate the participants more efficiently when they watched a lengthier duration of a horror movie (a film that needed to be certified by a horror specialist initially) throughout the experiment. Furthermore, having the participants watch in the same setting with the same ambiance would suffice. Based on our findings, the scope of this study will aid us in determining a person's anxiety level.

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Appendix A

Experimental Instructions Guide Script

[GREETINGS]

Experimenter: Hello, dear participants! Welcome to our session this afternoon. How are you?

Participants: (Response)

[BRIEFING]

Experimenter: All right! So, you are all gathered here today because you will be taking part in an experiment that we, 2nd year college students, are conducting. Our experiment revolves around anxiety and horror movies. We would like to clarify that all students present here today have agreed to the informed consent we sent and voluntarily take part in today's experiment.

Experimenter: To give you an idea, this experiment is a one-group pretest-post test design. You are 15 participants here in this experimental room right now. This experiment will take an hour. During the experiment, please make sure that there is

no distraction around you so you can focus. Also, please keep your cameras open during the entire experiment and mute your mics.

Experimenter: So, this is what will happen later. First, we will let you answer a Google form. The link will be provided in the Teams chat. Just click it so you will be directed to the form. It is just a short form and can be answered within five minutes. When you are done submitting the form, we will let you watch a short movie. Once the movie is done, we will provide another Google form that you will answer. Same process- the link will be sent in the chat, and you will click it.

Experimenter: Please do not worry because there will be no wrong answer. All you must do is answer the forms honestly.

Experimenter: Before we start, may I ask if everybody was able to understand what we will be doing today? Can you raise a virtual hand so I will know if everybody really understood? If there are questions, you can unmute yourself now or just message in the chat.

Participants: (Response)

(Check if all participants raised a hand) (Answer questions when there is any)

Experimenter: All right! I see that we are all in one page now. You can lower your hands.

[EXPERIMENT PROPER]

Experimenter: At this point, we request everyone to open their cameras and keep their mics muted.

(Wait till everyone has opened their cameras and muted their microphones before proceeding)

Experimenter: Let us check first how you are feeling right now through a Google form we will be providing. The link is in the chat. Please click it and give it a thumbs up if it is working. If you have not seen it yet, please inform us. You can start answering and make sure to click submit

when you are done. This is just short and will take approximately five minutes. So, do not worry and just take your time.

(Wait and monitor the input of responses. Close the form when everyone has submitted.)

Experimenter: All right! Everyone has submitted the forms already. At this point, you are going to watch a horror movie. It will be short. Just sit back. We will play the movie and you just watch. But before that, make sure that there is no distraction around you while you are watching so you can focus on the movie. Is everyone set? Can I get a thumbs up?

Participants: (Response)

Experimenter: All right! Let us start. (Play the movie)

(Wait until the movie is done while monitoring the participants)

Experimenter: All right! That is where the movie ends. Now, we will send another google form link in the chat. Please click it and answer. Once you are done, make sure to click submit. Please answer the form honestly and take your time.

(Wait for the participants to be done while monitoring the input of responses)

[DEBRIEFING]

Experimenter: All right! Everyone is done answering the form already. It ends our experiment. At this point, we would like you to breathe and just relax because we are finally done. So, what we have done earlier is for us to see how horror movies affect our anxiety level. We let you answer an anxiety scale before and after watching a horror movie to see whether there is a difference in your responses that may tell us the impact of horror movies on anxiety.

[CLOSING]

Experimenter: At this point, we would like to express our sincerest gratitude for taking part in our experiment and allowing us to borrow some of your time. Today is a rest day, yet you still showed up and took the experiment seriously. Please know you have helped our group so much. We would like to assure you also that your responses are held confidential and will be shared among the experimenters only. Again, thank you very much and good afternoon. You may leave the room now.

Appendix B

Flow Chart

Preparation

- The researcher will conduct the experiment at 1pm to 2pm.
- Send the MS Teams link
- Participants will be given a 5-minute preparation time.

Subject's Arrival

- Before conducting the experiment, the researcher will check if all participants already joined the meeting.

Subject's Installation

- Pre-test, post-test

Instructions

• After explaining the instructions, the participants will be given a chance to

groups and will then be analyzed.

Payment
The researchers will do a raffle and each participant involved in the experiment will be given a special certificate for their contributions.

End of the session.

Instructions

- After explaining the instructions, the participants will be given a chance to ask questions or clarifications (if any) before starting the experiment.
- Researchers will make sure to entertain any concerns of the participants before proceeding to the experiment.

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Main Experiment

- The experiment will be held virtually. The researchers randomly selected 16 participants

Treatment 1 – The group will take a STAI scale pretest

Treatment 2 – After watching a horror film the participants will take the STAI scale again as posttest

I feel at ease				
I feel upset				
I am presently worrying over misfortunes				
I feel satisfied				
I feel frightened				
I feel uncomfortable				
I feel self-confident				
I feel nervous				
I feel Jittery				
I feel indecisive				
I feel content				
I am relaxed				
I feel confused				
I am worried				
I feel steady				
I feel pleasant				